

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF THE COMPUTER NETWORKS SECURITY LEVEL BASED ON PETRI NETS & A SET OF PARAMETERS

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Abstract

This paper presents the usage of Petri Nets system to derive a set of parameters based on the simulation numerical results. Those parameters are Reliability of Service (RoS), Defense Factor (DF), Risk Factor (RF) and Modified Risk assessment law (RM) and those parameters can be used to assess different aspects of computer networks, especially those networks that are based on the Software-Defined Networks paradigm. The numerical results are gained from simulation conducted on three modelled proposed SDN topologies, which are Serial, Parallel and Hybrid topologies and, the single-controller Ordinary topology was used as a reference point. After that comes a comparison between those three proposed topologies based on these parameters that were derived from the simulation conducted on the modelling of those same topologies. The conclusion made based on that comparison, will show the best topology that can be used by SDN paradigm and can be most reliable against different threats. Based on the proposed parameters, it was possible to measure the performance of suggested SDN topologies and the results showed that the Parallel topology is the best of all the suggested ones as compared to the Ordinary topology in terms of the four parameters.

Keywords: Distributed Denial of Service, Defense Factor, Generalized Stochastic Petri Nets, Modified Risk Assessment, Reliability of Service, Risk Factor, Software-Defined Networks.

1. Introduction

As mentioned before in other published papers [1][2], there were three SDN controllers' topologies proposed in our research, in order to overcome some issues in SDN like Single Point of Failure (SPOF) and to provide better reliability in network structure to be able to deter cyber-threats like Man In The Middle (MITM) and Denial of Service/Distributed Denial of Service (DoS/DDoS) attacks [3].

The proposed topologies are Serial, Parallel and Hybrid. The fourth topology was an existing one and widely used which is mentioned in the research for the sake of comparison and to show the advantage of the proposed topologies over the usual topology which is labeled in this research as Ordinary topology. Those topologies differ between each other in the type of interaction they have between their controllers and in the way their controllers manage the network. To the best of our knowledge there isn't much work done to measure computer networks' performance mathematically; especially Software-Defined Networks and that's why it is needed to create a method for modelling the SDN behavior; especially the behavior of the proposed topologies and use it later to assess the network structure reliability and performance against cyber threats especially, Denial of Service/ Distributed Denial of Service (DoS/DDoS) attacks.

For that purpose, this research has proposed to simulate the topologies using Petri Nets system [4] and to do that, a software called Platform Independent Petri Nets Editor (PIPE) was used to model the SDN topologies, since its work basis is the usage of Petri Nets system. After the simulation, the software grants numerical results that were used later in our research to show the performance of the proposed three SDN topologies and their advantage over the Ordinary topology. Those

results were used to derive a relationship between the SDN controllers and their performance based on the monitoring of the diverse behavior patterns of those topologies against DoS/DDoS attacks and how many switch requests their controllers can deal with per unit of time.

From those mathematical relationships, it was possible to extrapolate some factors or parameters that based on them it is possible to assess various aspects of the security level of network performance. The proposed parameters are as follows:

1. Reliability of Service (RoS).
2. Defense Factor (DF).
3. Risk Factor (RF).
4. Modified Risk assessment (RM).

2. Materials used

This paper mainly discusses the usage of Petri Nets modelling of three proposed software-defined multi-controller topologies that differ in their way of interaction between their controllers and using that modelling, we'll be able to derive a set of parameters that all can be used to assess different aspects of computer networks especially, those based on SDN paradigm. Those parameters could show computer network performance against different cyber-threats like (DoS/DDoS) attacks. The modelled topologies were modelled using a software tool called Platform Independent Petri Nets Editor (PIPE) was used. PIPE is based on Markov chain and leverages petri nets system. The main module that will be used in PIPE is Generalized Stochastic Petri Nets (GSPN) to determine the feasibility and reliability of the proposed topologies. GSPN is a module of six tuples (P, T, F, W, M₀, and λ) [5].

3. Proposed algorithms

In previous paper [6], we have discussed the suggested algorithms that could be used by SDN controllers to create a more stable environment against cyber-threats like DoS/DDoS attacks. Those algorithms are as follows:

- Algorithms' suite integrated in HYDRA framework
- Secured channel of VPN algorithm
- Cryptography of Double RSA algorithm
- Distributed ledger concept of Blockchain algorithm

4. Proposed Topologies

As mentioned in previous articles like [7]; this research proposes three different topologies of Software-Defined Networks' controllers and compares them with the existing single-controller topology that was named as the Ordinary topology which was used as a reference point for comparison. The three proposed topologies are as follows:

- Serial Topology
- Parallel Topology
- Hybrid Topology

The figures below, show the proposed topologies alongside the Ordinary topology, starting with the Serial topology:

Figure 1. Structure of the Serial Topology.

And the Parallel topology will be depicted as in the following figure:

Figure 2. Structure of the Parallel Topology.

While the Hybrid topology will be shown as follows:

Figure 3. Structure of the Hybrid Topology.

The Ordinary topology can be depicted as in the figure below:

Figure 4. Structure of the Ordinary Topology.

5. Petri Nets Modelling:

Petri Nets were created in order to represent chemical reactions. For step-based procedural systems like concurrent execution systems and iteration processes, Petri nets technique provides a notation on a graphical basis. There is a mathematical explanation for this method. Petri nets' theoretical feature enables accurate modeling and analysis of system behavior [8]. In order

to gain a better understanding of the topologies' capabilities and limitations as well as to extrapolate a mathematical definition from the behavior of the three proposed SDN models, this study illustrates the use of petri nets to model these SDN controller models or structures. The modelling of topologies using PIPE software can be depicted as in the following figures for the proposed topologies and the Ordinary one respectively:

Figure 5. Serial topology modeling using Petri Nets

Figure 6. Parallel topology modeling using Petri Nets

Figure 7. Hybrid topology modeling using Petri Nets

Figure 8. Ordinary topology modeling using Petri Nets

Based on the modelling of those topologies using the GSPN module option in the PIPE software, it was possible to gain the following results as shown in Table 1:

Table 1
Average Number of Tokens (distribution intensity of tokens) in Places Representing SDN Controllers Using GSPN Module

No	Places	Serial topology		Parallel topology		Hybrid topology		Ordinary topology	
		No. of controllers	Tokens Z_{K_i}						
1	P1			1	0	1	0	1	2.0
2	P5			1	0	1	0		
3	P3	1	0.16						
4	P7	1	0.06						
5	P9			1	0	1	0		
6	P11	1	0.13						
7	P21					1	0.90		
8	P22					1	0.90		
9	P26					1	0.90		
Total		3	0.36	3	0	6	2.71	1	2.0

Based on the modelling results of those topologies, it was possible to extrapolate four main security parameters that based on them, it's possible to evaluate the performance of the computer networks that are based on the SDN paradigm, especially those that based on the proposed models. The proposed factors or parameters are:

- Reliability of Service (RoS).

Is an expression added in this research to describe the performance reliability of data protection. Reliability of Service (RoS) could be close to Quality of Service (QoS) which is the definition of the performance of any system's service, like a computer network or a cloud computing, etc. The SDN has many positive features. These features have attracted the attention of researchers to improve the QoS provisioning of today's various network applications [9]. But RoS is a little bit different and has a more detailed specification tailored for the needs of SDN. This work proposes to measure the RoS as follows:

$$\text{RoS} = 1 - \text{TANR} / \text{TANR}_0 \quad (1)$$

Where TANR is the Total Average Number of network requests of the proposed topologies, which is the summation of all averages after dividing them by the number of these averages and that means how many requests per server and shows the risk occurrence level. The TANR_0 is the Total Average Number or intensity of requests in controller of Ordinary topology.

- Defense Factor (DF).

To determine the strength and security feasibility of the network against DoS/DDoS attacks. In terms of Petri Nets, the requests will be represented by how many tokens are there in specific places which in turn represent specific nodes in the software-defined network and those specific nodes of interest are the SDN controllers. In the equation (4) places representing the SDN controllers are denoted as K, where $K \in P$, P is the whole group of places in the Petri Nets (PN) model, which in turn is a tuple of 5 objects, $\text{PN} = \{P, T, I, O, M_0\}$, where P is the finite set of places, T is a finite set of transitions, I is the input function, O for output function and M_0 is the initial marking.

$$K = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} K_i, K_i \in \{1 - n\} \quad (2)$$

$$Z = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} Z_i, Z_i \in \{0 - \infty\} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{DF} = [\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} K_i] / [\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} Z_i] = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} \left[\frac{K_i}{Z_i} \right] \quad (4)$$

The Defense Factor DF equation depends mainly on the assessment of the strength of software-defined network's controllers based on their emptiness and that means their readiness and availability to deter any kind of DoS/DDoS attack. Therefore, it is logical to say that the more controllers we have the better the network's capability it is to deter those attacks. That means the more controllers the better and the higher DF value it is, and that explains why the DF equation has the places that represent the controllers in numerator position because the number of controllers is proportional to the value of the DF.

While on the other hand we can see that the more tokens that represent the requests, the weaker the network gets and that means the less DF value we will get.

So, the DF value and the number of tokens or requests are inversely proportional and that's why they should be put in the denominator position. In addition, it is mentioning worthy that if we reversed the DF then, meaning if we divided the tokens/requests by the places/controllers then we'll get how many requests per server meaning; it will divide them equally and that could be unrealistic, because based on the types of reactions between the controllers in every topology; a controller could be dealing with more requests while the other is just waiting as a backup controller.

- Risk Factor (RF).

To figure out the weakness level of the network environment. The values of the Total Average Number (distribution intensity) of Requests (TANR), can be described as the Risk Factor. Since we need to find the strength and defense ability of the network controllers to deter the DoS/DDoS attacks and the more PN tokens/network requests controllers have per unit of time, the more occupied the controllers will be and the weaker they will be and this shows the weakness point or risk level of the network.

So, this paper shows the proposes the Risk Factor (RF) parameter to evaluate the efficiency of the elaborated topologies. The relationship that depicts the parameter is as follows:

$$RF = 1 / DF \quad (5)$$

Where DF, is the Defense Factor value of the measured topology. The parameter RF will still be the opposite of what we need to figure out, which is the TANR also. So, the quantity number of PN places/SDN controllers should be in the numerator and the Petri Nets tokens/ network requests should be in the denominator and that is another logical proof of why there was a need to derive that formula and to put it in that form.

- Modified Risk assessment (RM).

To assess the security level of software-defined networks based on the risk assessment law, it is possible to modify it for the needs of SDN and after modifications, it's called the modified law of security risk assessment (RM). By applying the security risk assessment law [10] to evaluate the protection level of the computer networks, which states:

$$R = P_0 * V \quad (6)$$

Where R is the security risk assessment that quantifies and shows the possibility of a threat acting upon a vulnerability successfully and the severity of the results of that attack, P_0 represents the initial probability or likelihood of the vulnerability occurrence and V represents the value or cost of the asset.

In other words, using this formula we can estimate how much the proposed framework will reduce the security risk of a computer network, hence assuring its security. Since a server is the most important part and has the highest value node in the network environment,

in which we will install our controller software, then we can say it has the highest asset value or impact. The servers have the value $V=100$ as an asset impact [10], because it is the value of server's impact on the secure socket layer (SSL) which is the same layer which the OpenFlow protocol works through.

The probability of vulnerability $P_0 = 0.025$ which is measured based on the lost orders due to the web server denial of service attack. It is possible to acquire a new value of probability P_n , which will be affected by the DF mathematically as shown:

$$P_n = P_0 / DF \quad (7)$$

The higher Defense Factor, the better which is the opposite of the probability of vulnerability; that means that they should be inversely proportional mathematically as they're logically and that's why they're positioned this way in the formula of finding the new likelihood or probability of vulnerability.

It is possible to estimate that our framework and the formula derived from its modeling, will reduce the likelihood of attacks occurrence (like DoS/DDoS attacks) and for that we propose a modified version of Security Risk Assessment parameter and it will be as:

$$RM = P_n * V \quad (8)$$

6. Comparison of parameters of SDN topologies security assessment

Eventually there is a need to provide an analytical comparison of the proposed parameters of computer networks security assessment based on the suggested topologies and the results of their simulation. The data are presented in Table 2, where RoS is the Reliability of Service, DF is the Defense Factor, RF is the Risk Factor, RM is the Modified security Risk assessment.

Table 2

The values of RoS, DF, RF, RM and cost for the proposed topologies

No.	Topology	RoS	DF	RF	RM
1	Serial Topology	0.94	8.23	0.12	0.3
2	Parallel Topology	1.0	∞	0	0
3	Hybrid Topology	0.78	2.21	0.45	1.1
4	Ordinary Topology		0.50	2.0	5.0

From the data presented in Table 2, it is possible to infer that the Parallel topology is the best one from the point of view of all security estimation parameters, after that comes the Serial topology and the Hybrid topology is the last one.

The usage circumstances of these parameters differ from each other. When it is needed to measure the data protection performance then, it is possible to apply the RoS parameter, where it is possible to infer that the reliability of service of the serial topology is 0.94 of the previous Reliability of service of the single-controller ordinary topology, the parallel topology gained a 100% enhancement as compared to the ordinary topology and the hybrid topology proved to be better than the ordinary topology as well in terms of reliability of service by 0.78.

In other words, it is possible to say that the best topology of all the proposed topologies in terms of RoS, is the parallel topology.

When there's a need to determine the defense ability and the network's strength against DoS/DDoS attacks then, it is possible to depend on the DF parameter. Where the defense factor that shows the strength of presented SDN topologies against DoS/DDoS attacks has the value of 8.23, while the parallel topology has a very high value close to ∞ since the number of the tokens that represent network requests in its controllers, are very small and close to 0 most of the processing time and that means that the defense factor value of this topology is close to optimal, meaning the parallel topology is nearly most reliable against DoS/DDoS attacks, the hybrid topology has a value of 2.21 and last but not least the ordinary topology has the least value which is 0.50, meaning that the single-controller topology has the weakest structure against DoS/DDoS attacks.

While if there was a need to reverse the situation and figure out the weakness of the network then, it is possible to reverse the parameter and use the RF which is the inversely proportional to DF. So that means the

higher the value, the worse it is. It is possible to conclude that the serial topology has the value of 0.12, the risk factor value of the parallel topology is 0 since it is nearly optimal and that means this structure has low risk, the hybrid topology has a risk factor of 0.45 and least but not last the ordinary topology has the highest value of 2.0, which refers to the high jeopardy the comes along the usage of this topology.

In case there was a need to measure the SDN environment weakness based on the computer networks law, then it is possible to modify it to be used based on the proposed SDN environments and their Petri Nets modeling and in this case the RM parameter can be used. This parameter is a proof of how the DF equation has assured the security of the proposed topologies and reduced the risk value as compared to the already existing ordinary topology in terms of the risk assessment law that is used to describe the security risk for computer networks in general. So after modifying the risk assessment law by incorporating the effect of the Defense Factor in its equation to create a new parameter called the Modified Risk parameter, the research shows that the serial topology has a reduced RM value of 0.3, the parallel topology has a value of 0 as well hence, it is the best topology of all the suggested topologies, the hybrid topology's RM value is 1.1 and the single-controller topology has a value of 5.0 and this high RM value of the ordinary topology shows the security enhancements, the proposed topologies have in their design over the ordinary topology.

The novelty of these proposed parameters stems from their basis, which is the modeling of the suggested SDN topologies using Petri Nets (PN) system to simulate their behavior and to acquire numerical results from that. Based on these numerical results, those parameters were provided.

Alongside the algorithms, topologies, and their Petri Nets modeling, this research provides mathematical mechanisms to evaluate the security level and data protection performance of computer networks based on SDN technologies.

7. Conclusions

This work concentrates on increasing the software-defined network's protection hence, turning SDN into a more protected environment, leading to protecting networks generally if those networks leverage the SDN structure.

The paper here, shows a brief description of the proposed algorithms and topologies suggested for Software-Defined Networks' controllers to overcome some issues that SDN paradigm is facing like Single Point of Failure (SPOF), Denial of Service/Distributed Denial of Service (DoS/DDoS) and (MITM) attacks.

After that, this paper gives modelling for the proposed SDN topologies using Petri Nets (PN) system. The proposed topologies are named as the Serial, Parallel and Hybrid topologies. Also, for the sake of comparison, there was another modelling given for an existing single-controller topology named in this research as the Ordinary topology.

The PN modelling was conducted using Platform Independent Petri Nets Editor (PIPE) software that has many modules including Generalized Stochastic Petri Nets (GSPN) module which is the one that was used.

Findings: the numerical results gained from the GSPN module were used to extrapolate mathematical tools that were measuring the security and performance level of computer networks based on four parameters. Those parameters are Reliability of Service (RoS), Defense Factor (DF), Risk Factor (RF) and Modified Risk assessment law (RM). Based on those parameters it's possible to estimate the reliability of SDN-based computer networks against some cyber-threats like DoS/DDoS attacks.

Research limitations/implications: this paper opens the discussion *about* the measurement of network security and the ability to model network risk using different performance evaluation parameters which could be used to determine the network ability to deter cyber-attacks especially DoS/DDoS attacks.

Practical implications: this paper argues about the ability to use the results acquired from the Generalized Stochastic Petri Nets (GSPN) module in the PIPE software to derive parameters that can measure the level of network performance and deterrence ability against DoS/DDoS attacks.

Originality/value: of the work is determined by the developed formulas, which have a big contribution for the SDN community by figuring out a way to deal with the issue of modelling software-defined network's performance using a set of parameters and topologies.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

Annex 1. Example of simulation process of Petri Nets Model of Parallel Topology using PIPE software.

Annex 2. Table showing the Average number of tokens (network requests) on a place (main controller) for the Parallel topology as an example.

Average Number of Tokens on a Place

Place	Number of Tokens
P0	0.23658
P1	0
P10	0.10948
P11	0.78103
P12	0.32674
P13	0.32664
P14	0
P15	0.32669
P16	0.32663
P17	0.32674
P18	0.1093
P19	0.10933
P2	0.1093
P20	0.10948
P3	0.78139
P4	0.23664
P5	0
P6	0.10933
P7	0.78134
P8	0.23711
P9	0

Annex 3. Simulation process of Petri Nets Model of Ordinary Topology.

Annex 4. Table showing the Average number of tokens (network requests) on a place (main controller) for the Ordinary topology.

Average Number of Tokens on a Place

Place	Number of Tokens
P0	0
P1	0
P2	0
P3	2
P4	0
P5	1
P6	0
P7	0

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